

Open Science NL

Open Research Software Advisory Panel

Meeting Agenda

20 February 2026, 15:00-17:00

Location: [MS Teams](#)

Attendees

- Ana Martinovici
- Daniel S. Katz
- Daniela Gawehns
- John Swinbank
- Karthik Ram
- Laurents Sesink
- Martine de Vos
- Mateusz Kuzak
- Morane Gruenpeter
- Santosh Ilamparuthi
- Thomas Pronk
- Vincent Traag
- Mark van Assem - Acting Co-Chair
- Marta Teperek (MT) - Acting Chair

Apologies

- Maria Cruz, Chair

Agenda

15.00 - 15.05 – Welcome and agenda

- Minutes of the last meeting have been published on Zenodo:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18151097>

15.05 – 15.10 – Actions of the previous meeting

- Meeting with the NWO Advisory Panel Computer Science to discuss support for open source software project is scheduled for 15 April. Ana and Vincent are attending.
- The Open Science NL Steering Board advised to merge the Open Research Software and FAIR Data panels (next steps are subject of today's discussion)

15.10 - 15.15 - Update on the implementation of the OSNL Work Programme 2024-2025

- Open Science Infrastructure and Replication Studies Programme calls were awarded
- Funding to the NLeSC for the Research Software Sustainability Programme was awarded
- The decision on the Research on Open Science call for proposals will be made on 20 March

15.15 - 16.45 – Advisory panel – going forward

The Open Science NL Steering Board advised to merge the Open Research Software and FAIR Data panels into a single advisory panel.

To ensure that there is sufficient time and space to discuss matters which are relevant only to research software and only to research data, the Board advised to:

- Allocate sufficient time in the agenda for discussions pertaining to open research software/research data
- Consider adding a few additional members (above 12) if additional expertise turns out to be necessary
- Consider planning separate meetings dedicated to software/data if this becomes necessary/desirable

The name of the merged panel needs to be inclusive of the broadened scope of the merged panel.

Planning of dedicated agenda items and dedicated meetings

Any panel member can suggest new agenda items or dedicated meetings. For adding agenda items within, suggestions need to be made in writing at least 2 weeks before the meeting date via an email to the chair of the meeting.

Expertise of panel members

Panel members are asked to advise whether the merged panel will continue to have sufficient content expertise pertaining to open research software. *Appendix 1: Profiles panel members* details the desired profiles of panel members as per the current OSNL Community Engagement Strategy.

Panel members are asked if:

- Is the key expertise as detailed in *Appendix 1: Profiles panel members* up to date, or is any key area of expertise missing? (if so, which expertise is missing?)
- Given that the tenure of panel members which were appointed for 2 years will end (see the table below), is there any expertise missing within the merged panel? If so, what is the missing expertise?

Note that the decision how to proceed with regards to the latter can only be made jointly during the first meeting of the joint advisory panel.

Terms of Open Research Software panel members

Name and surname	Term (years)
Daniela Gawehns	2
Laurents Sesink	2
John D. Swinbank	2
Daniel S. Katz	3
Karthik Ram	2
Ana Martinovici	3
Santosh Ilamparuthi	3
Vincent Traag	2
Thomas Pronk	3
Morane Gruenpeter	3
Martine de Vos	3
Mateusz Kuzak	2

Name of the panel

Given the expanded scope of the merged panel, the name of the panel should also change.

Do panel members have suggestions? (suggestions made by the FAIR Data panel during its meeting on 17 February will be shared during the meeting)

Tenure of remaining panel members

Would any of the panel members whose term expires in 2027 (panel members appointed for 3 years) be prepared to stay for an additional year? (4 years total) This would help ensure continuity of the work of the panel and prevent an event that all panel members step down at the same time in 2027.

16.45 – 16.50 – Thank you to the outgoing panel members

16.50 – 16.55 – Any other business

16.55 – 17.00: Meeting close

Appendix 1 – Profiles panel members

Open Research Software Advisory Panel

The advisory panel on open research software will consist of individuals with expertise and experience in, but not limited to, the following areas relevant to open research software:

- Training and skills for open research software
- Infrastructures and tools for open research software
- Software sustainability
- Open source software
- FAIR software
- Computational reproducibility
- Software publication and citation
- Software management and software management plans
- Licences for software
- Community building
- Open research software in the context of a university
- Open research software in the context of a university medical centre
- Open research software in the context of a university of applied sciences
- Open research software in the context of a knowledge / research institute

The panel will have representation from diverse disciplines and diverse roles, including researchers, research software engineers, research support staff and policy experts.

All members of the panel are able to provide substantive input and give direction to the open research software line of Open Science NL. Members will:

- Provide independent advice and contribute expertise and insights. In doing so, they act independently of the institution they are affiliated with.
- Have insight into the open research software landscape nationally and internationally.
- Have complementary expertise, so that the panel as a whole covers a broad range of knowledge, experience and expertise.
- Keep abreast of developments in the area of open research software and its relation to other areas of open science, and in relation to their respective disciplines or areas of expertise.

FAIR data advisory panel

The advisory panel on FAIR data will consist of individuals with expertise and experience in, but not limited to, the following areas relevant to FAIR data:

- Training and skills for FAIR data
- Infrastructures and tools for FAIR data
- Metadata and ontologies
- Confidential data (including privacy-sensitive data, as well as other types of data)
- Open Hardware
- FAIR data in the context of a university
- FAIR data in the context of a university medical centre
- FAIR data in the context of a university of applied sciences
- FAIR data in the context of a knowledge institute

All members of the FAIR data advisory panel are able to give substantive direction to the FAIR data programme line of the Open Science NL. In addition, the following requirements apply:

- They can explain the importance of FAIR data from the perspective of their field/area of expertise and are able to assess proposals for the implementation of FAIR data.
- They have insight into FAIR data landscape (national and international).
- Group members complement each other.
- Members keep in touch with the work fields and knowledge areas.
- They share their content and/or context expertise and act independently of the institution they are affiliated with.